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Review Article

Timing - Understanding Central and Peripheral Clocks

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Stepien JM,^a Coates A^{a,b}, Banks S.^a

a Sleep and Chronobiology Laboratory, Behaviour-Brain-Body Research Group, UniSA: Justice & Society, University of South Australia, Adelaide, South Australia

b Alliance for Research in Exercise, Nutrition, and Activity, UniSA: Allied Health & Human Performance, University of South Australia, Adelaide, South Australia

Abstract

From the discovery of the first clock genes outside of the 'master clock' – the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) – to now, there has been extensive research into the location of these peripheral clocks and how they relate to the SCN and other timing signals. The purpose of this review is to provide an overview of the current knowledge in this area. Areas discussed will include: How the timing of sleep and wake in mammals is controlled by the central clock; how physiological processes during sleep and wake in mammals are coordinated by peripheral clocks; what changes in environmental signals affect the timing of SCN and peripheral clocks; how we measure central and peripheral clock timing; which environmental signals can entrain the SCN and peripheral clocks; and how disturbances in central and peripheral clock timing due to aspects of modern lifestyles including shiftwork and jet lag, as well as biological aspects such as blindness and chronotype, may have negative impacts on our health. By understanding how our biological timing systems work, we may be able to develop strategies to minimise disturbances in central and peripheral clock timing and therefore the associated negative health outcomes observed.

Keywords

Circadian rhythm; suprachiasmatic nucleus; peripheral clocks; clock genes; circadian disruption

1. Introduction

This review is designed to give an overview of the current understanding of how the body coordinates functions over the 24 hour period. It will look at why a timing system is advantageous, how timing is coordinated in mammals, what factors may influence timing in mammals, how we measure timing, and how disturbances in timing may be responsible for negative health outcomes in humans.

The day/night cycle offers a stable and dependable measure of time for a species to segment activity to regular periods. Different species have adapted to different sleep/wake patterns (such as being diurnal or nocturnal) due to a number of factors. Doing so favours survival by maximising activity efficiency – increasing activity when food and prey availability is maximal and predator risk is minimal, and decreasing energy expenditure when food and prey availability is minimal and predator risk is maximal (1). In turn, when an organism is active, metabolic processes are coordinated to harvest energy. During rest periods, metabolism switches to releasing energy stores to ensure adequate energy is available for various maintenance processes.

When mammals are not awake and seeking out food they use a large amount of their rest time to sleep. There are a number of theories that support the importance of sleep and the functions that occur during the sleep period. Sleep has been proposed to assist with a number of processes including brain plasticity (2), learning, and memory (3), thermoregulation providing brain and body cooling (4), tissue repair (5), immune functioning (6), energy conservation (7), and neuronal detoxification (8).

Adult humans, on average, spend 36% of time asleep and 64% awake (9). It has been demonstrated that when humans do not get enough sleep on a regular basis they are less able to maintain a healthy energy balance. Five days of inadequate sleep has been found to lead to an approximate 5% increase in total daily energy expenditure as well as an increase in energy intake above what is required to maintain energy balance (10). In relation to general health and wellbeing sleep quality, rather than sleep quantity, positively correlates with measures of physical and psychological health (11).

2. The timing of sleep and wake in mammals is controlled by the central clock

Although mammals have different sleep/wake patterns, mechanisms of circadian timing are highly conserved. The central clock is located in the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) in the anterior hypothalamus of the brain. The cells of the SCN contain a number of 'clock' genes that are able to keep time by transcriptional/translational feedback loops that operate on an approximate 24 hour cycle (12). The primary genes involved in this process are *Clock* (circadian locomotor output cycles kaput), *Bmal1* (brain and muscle arnt-like protein-1, also known as *Arntl*), *Cry* (cryptochrome) 1 and 2, and *Per* (period) 1, 2, and 3 for the primary positive loop. Secondary loop genes include *Rev-ERBa* (reverse strand of ERBA alpha, also known as *Nr1d1*), *Rev-ERBβ* (reverse strand of ERBA beta, also known as *Nr1d2*), *RORα* (retinoic acid receptor-related orphan receptor alpha, also known as *Nr1F1*), *RORβ* (retinoic acid receptor-related orphan receptor beta, also known as *Nr1F2*), and *RORγ* (retinoic acid receptor-related orphan receptor gamma, also known as *Nr1F3*). When cultured in the lab, SCN cells show robust rhythmicity for several weeks (13).

In the absence of time cues, the central clock has its own genetically determined 'free run'. This means that without any indication of what the time of day is, the SCN is able to generate a regular rhythm to maintain the timing of physiological processes within an organism to maintain homeostasis. In rats this 'free run' has been reported to be around 24.4 hours (14) and in mice around 23.6 hours (15) while in humans the average free run period is 24.2 hours (16-18). The primary zeitgeber (timegiver) in mammals is sunlight that synchronises, or entrains, the central clock every 24 hours to ensure physiological processes align with the environmental light/dark cycle (Figure 1). Light entrains the SCN utilising non-visual pathways via the retina to regulate the transcriptional/translational feedback loop by activating the transcription of *Per* genes.

In both animal models and humans, changes in light exposure have been shown to re-entrain, or phase shift, SCN activity in a dose dependent manner. Phase-response curves of locomotor activity in rodents (20), melatonin in rats (21) and humans (22), and core body temperature in humans (23)

Figure 1. The non-visual pathway of light from the environment to the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) and how it regulates the timing of the transcriptional/translational feedback loop (19). Once the light signal reaches the cells of the SCN, it is the induction of *Per1* and *Per2* gene expression that synchronises SCN timing with the environment.

in response to light show that when kept under constant lighting conditions, only light presented during subjective darkness (the time that the SCN is signalling to the body that it is night time) can phase shift these rhythms. Light presented during the subjective day (the time that the SCN is signalling to the body that it is daytime) has no phase shifting effect. When light is presented during the first half of the subjective night, the onset of the phase marker measured will delay (occur later) the following day. Conversely, when light is presented during the second half of the subjective night, the onset of the phase marker being measured will advance (occur earlier) the following day. It has also been shown that the degree of phase shift light exposure can elicit depends on the time of exposure (22), length of exposure (24), and intensity of exposure (25). It has also been shown that the wavelength of light presented can affect the degree of phase shift with shorter wavelengths (blue/green) more effective than longer wavelengths (26), and that intensities as low as 50 lux can both acutely suppress SCN activity and phase shift SCN activity on the following night (25).

While the evidence above demonstrates that the SCN is the master clock that signals to the rest of the body environmental light information, there is also evidence that clock gene expression is not exclusive to the SCN.

3. Physiological processes during sleep and wake in mammals are co-ordinated by peripheral clocks

Along with the SCN, there are a number peripheral clocks that have been identified in almost all organs. These clocks also use the transcriptional/translational feedback loop system to coordinate physiological processes at the cellular, organ, and system level. Unlike the SCN, peripheral clock cells grown in the lab lose their rhythmicity after a few days (13, 27). Furthermore, studies in rats (28) and mice (29, 30) where the SCN has been removed have demonstrated that in the absence of the SCN, peripheral clock gene expression is no longer rhythmic. As a result, peripheral clocks need to receive signals from the SCN to maintain rhythmicity and this is achieved via a number of different pathways, evidence of which is detailed below.

3.1. The Autonomic Nervous System

The autonomic nervous system provides a direct pathway between the SCN and target organs. Identified targets include the submandibular salivary glands (31, 32), liver (33-35), pancreas (31), lung (36) and adrenal glands (31, 37, 38). The regulation of these tissues, both sympathetic and parasympathetic, have been directly traced from the SCN to target peripheral tissues (39).

3.2. Melatonin

Melatonin is a hormone produced and released into the circulation by the pineal gland. This release is controlled by the SCN via the sympathetic nervous system with minimal levels circulating during the day and maximal levels reached during the night. Melatonin synchronises peripheral clocks with the SCN, acting as a global zeitgeber that controls the transcription/translation cycle of peripheral clock genes. This has been demonstrated in both cell culture (40) and in animal models (41). The mechanism by which melatonin synchronises peripheral clocks has not yet been elucidated but it has been suggested that melatonin may mediate its effects on peripheral clocks via post-transcriptional processes (42) and this in turn, may explain why phase shifts occur more slowly in peripheral clocks than in the SCN.

3.3. Glucocorticoids

Glucocorticoids (corticosterone in rodents, cortisol in humans) are hormones produced in the adrenal gland and this release is controlled by the SCN via the sympathetic nervous system. Glucocorticoid response elements have been found to be located in the regulatory regions of mouse core clock genes *Bmal1*, *Cry1*, *Per1* (43, 44), and *Per2* (45) suggesting that glucocorticoid binding may lead to the transcriptional activation of these and other clock genes (46). While glucocorticoid receptors are expressed throughout the brain and periphery, the SCN does not express these

receptors (47). On their own, circulating glucocorticoids have been shown in the rat liver to maintain peripheral clock gene rhythmicity in the absence of autonomic nervous system input from the SCN or feeding signals, albeit with lower amplitude of expression (48). Exogenous administration of the glucocorticoid analogue dexamethasone has been shown to phase shift clock gene rhythms in rat peripheral tissues grown in the laboratory (49).

3.4. Temperature

The SCN controls the core body temperature rhythm in mammals (50). It has been shown that rat fibroblasts cells grown in the laboratory can maintain previously induced rhythms when exposed to the natural temperature rhythms measured in mice for a number of days compared to fibroblasts maintained at a constant temperature, but not establish a new rhythm in these cells (51). Temperature effects are most likely mediated by heat shock factor 1 (HSF1) which has been shown to oscillate in liver cells and modify its rhythm in line with temperature changes (52). The use of HSF1 inhibitors have been demonstrated to stop the shift in transcription of clock genes due to changes in temperature rhythms (53).

3.5. Behaviour

Behavioural processes such as locomotor activity and feeding are also influenced by the SCN in mammals (54, 55). These in turn can influence endocrine activity and body temperature. Under unrestricted feeding conditions, activity and feeding follow a regular rhythm in line with the SCN (and light/dark cycle).

As shown above, the SCN employs a number of ways to communicate environmental light information to the peripheral clocks to ensure physiological processes are appropriately coordinated during sleep and wake.

Figure 2. The differences in the timing of peak *Per1* expression in central and peripheral clocks as measured in mice over the 24 hour period drawn from data in Yamanaka et al. (56). This demonstrates that under normal circumstances the timing of *Per1* expression in each tissue is not precisely synchronised. Zeitgeber time (ZT) 0 is the time of exposure to the timegiver (in this case time of lights on). SCN=suprachiasmatic nucleus.

4. The measurement of central and peripheral clock timing

By measuring the timing of the acrophase (or peak) of clock gene expression researchers can compare the timing of different clocks within an organism. It has been demonstrated in mice that the *Per1* expression acrophase occurs at different times in different tissues (56) with the acrophase occurring in the SCN at zeitgeber time (ZT)6.5, the lung at ZT11.8, the liver at ZT15.1, and skeletal muscle at ZT15.8 (Figure 2).

Similar phenomena occur in humans. It has been demonstrated that different peripheral tissues have different acrophases for the same clock genes. Bjarnason and colleagues measured *Per1* expression in oral mucosa and skin and found that expression peaked at ZT0.5 and ZT6.7 respectively (57). Differences have also been demonstrated between leukocytes and beard hair follicles (58). In human cultured epidermal cells, it has also been demonstrated that different clock genes have different acrophases within the same cell types and that different cell functions can be mapped to these differing peaks (59). The cycling of gene expression may allow the separation of chemically incompatible reactions, for example, ensuring glycogen synthase and glycogen phosphorylase expression does not occur at the same time so that glycogen stores are built up when energy is being absorbed and broken down when energy is no longer being taken up (60). Peripheral clocks have been measured in a range of human tissues obtained from live individuals (Table 1).

Reliable measurements of central and peripheral clock timing mean we can examine how the clocks work together and determine what factors can influence or alter timing in clocks. The direct measurement of clock gene expression in humans is limited (see Table 1) as some tissues are not easily accessible to be sampled on multiple occasions. This limits the use of clock gene expression to determine how a particular factor may differentially affect clock timing in as many clocks as can be done in animal models.

Table 1. Human tissues where primary and secondary loop clock gene expression has been measured and the clock genes that were examined.

System	Tissue/Cell	Clock Gene Measured			Reference
Integumentary	hair follicle	<i>Bmal1</i> <i>Per1</i>	<i>Per2</i> <i>Per3</i>	<i>Rev-ERBa</i> <i>Rev-ERBβ</i>	(58, 61, 62)
	oral mucosa	<i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i>	<i>Rev-ERBa</i>	(57, 63-65)
	skin	<i>Bmal1</i>	<i>Per1</i>		(57)
	skin fibroblasts	<i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Cry2</i> <i>Per1</i>	<i>Per2</i> <i>Per3</i>	(66-69)
	skin keratinocytes	<i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i> <i>Cry2</i>	<i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i> <i>Per3</i>	<i>Rev-ERBa</i> <i>RORa</i>	(69)
	skin melanocytes	<i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i> <i>Cry2</i>	<i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i> <i>Per3</i>	<i>Rev-ERBa</i>	(69)
	epidermal stem cells	<i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i> <i>Cry2</i>	<i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i> <i>Per3</i>	<i>Rev-ERBa</i> <i>Rev-ERBβ</i>	(59)
Circulatory	whole blood	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i> <i>Cry2</i>	<i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i> <i>Per3</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i>	<i>Rev-ERBβ</i> <i>RORa</i>	(70-74)
	monocytes	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Cry2</i> <i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i>	<i>Per3</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i>	(75)
	mononuclear blood cells	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Cry2</i> <i>Per1</i> <i>Per2a</i>	<i>Per3</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i>	(76-85)
	leukocytes	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Cry2</i> <i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i>	<i>Per3</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i> <i>RORa</i>	(58, 85-91)
	lymphocytes	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Cry2</i> <i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i>	<i>Per3</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i>	(92)
	mast cells	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i>	<i>Cry1</i> <i>Per1</i>	<i>Per2</i>	(93)
	eosinophils	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i>	<i>Cry1</i> <i>Per1</i>	<i>Per2</i>	(93)
	CD4+ T-cells	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Cry2</i> <i>Per2</i> <i>Per3</i>	<i>Rev-ERBa</i> <i>RORa</i>	(94)
	polymorphonuclear cells	<i>Cry1</i> <i>Cry2</i>	<i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i>	<i>Per3</i>	(83, 85)
	papillary muscle cells	<i>Bmal1</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Per1</i> <i>Per2</i>		(95)
	Endocrine	pancreatic islet cells	<i>Clock</i> <i>Cry1</i>	<i>Per3</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i>	<i>Rev-ERBβ</i>
visceral adipose tissue		<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i>	<i>Cry1</i>	<i>Per2</i>	(97, 98)
subcutaneous adipose tissue		<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i>	<i>Cry1</i>	<i>Per2</i>	(97, 98)
Bone	CD4+ (haematopoietic) bone marrow cells	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i>	<i>Cry1</i> <i>Cry2</i>	<i>Per2</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i>	(99)
	whole bone marrow cell samples	<i>Clock</i> <i>Bmal1</i>	<i>Cry1</i> <i>Cry2</i>	<i>Per2</i> <i>Rev-ERBa</i>	(99)

Note: *Clock* (circadian locomotor output cycles kaput); *Bmal1* (brain and muscle arnt-like protein-1); *Cry1* (cryptochrome 1); *Cry2* (cryptochrome 2); *Per1* (period 1); *Per2* (period 2); *Per3* (period 3); *Rev-ERBa* (reverse strand of ERBA alpha); *Rev-ERBβ* (reverse strand of ERBA beta); *RORa* (retinoic acid receptor-related orphan receptor alpha).

Table 2. Evidence for the effect of identified entrainers on central and peripheral clock timing in humans and animal models.

Tissue where the clock is found	Model	Entrainers			
		Light	Activity	Temperature	Food
SCN	Animal	Yes	No	No	No (timing) Yes (caloric restriction 66%)
	Human	Yes	Yes (partial)	-	No (timing) Yes (caffeine)
Liver	Animal	Yes - rat and mouse	Yes - mouse	Yes/no - mouse	Yes (timing) - rat and mouse Yes (caffeine) - mouse
Pineal Gland	Animal	Yes - rat	-	-	-
Adrenal Gland	Animal	Yes - rat and mouse	-	-	-
	Human	Assumed (salivary cortisol)	-	-	-
Heart	Animal	Yes - rat	-	-	Yes (timing) - rat and mouse
Skeletal Muscle	Animal	Yes - rat and mouse	Yes - mouse	-	-
	Human	-	Possible	-	-
Lung	Animal	Yes - mouse	Yes - mouse	-	Yes (timing) - rat Yes (caffeine) - mouse
Hair Follicle	Human	Yes	-	-	-
Kidney	Animal	-	-	No - mouse	No (timing) - mouse Yes (caffeine) - mouse
Submandibular Gland	Animal	-	-	No - mouse	-
Pancreas	Animal	-	-	-	Unsure (timing) - mouse

Note: - indicates that no experiments have been done for this entrainer in this tissue. For food, (timing) refers to timed restricted feeding.

5. Is light the only signal that can entrain the SCN and peripheral clocks?

As shown above, light synchronises SCN activity. Recent work in animal models has looked at whether a change in light exposure can produce phase shifts in peripheral clocks similar to those in the SCN. When a one-hour light pulse is presented to rats during the subjective night, immediate changes to clock gene expression are seen in the pineal gland, adrenal gland, liver, heart, and muscle though the changes are not uniform in each tissue and are dependent on the time the light pulse is delivered (35). In mice, it has been shown that light exposure during the subjective night caused an immediate increase in *Per1* expression in the adrenal gland but had no immediate effect on *Per1* expression in the liver or kidney (38). A light-induced increase in salivary cortisol is also seen in humans in a phase dependent manner (100, 101) with morning light causing an increase but not evening exposure. This may be caused by an autonomic mediated increase in adrenal sensitivity to adrenocorticotropic hormone controlled by the SCN in a circadian manner (100). It should be noted that a corresponding change in peripheral clock timing can only be assumed as direct sampling of the human adrenal gland was not possible.

When examined together, previous work has demonstrated that a change in light schedule does shift both central and peripheral clock timing, but not to the same degree or direction, nor in the same timeframe (56, 102, 103). It has also been demonstrated in mice that different clock genes re-entrain to a change in light schedule at different rates within the same clock and there is no consistent pattern to this re-entrainment in different clocks (103). Why this is the case remains to be elucidated.

Researchers have examined whether there are other environmental factors that can influence the timing of central and peripheral clocks (Table 2). The following section considers factors other than light that can influence central and peripheral clock timing.

5.1. Activity

Activity, in the form of exercise, has been examined as a possible entrainer. In the SCN, previous experiments have shown that scheduled exercise can enhance the shift of behavioural rhythms to a change in light schedule in mice (a nocturnal animal). Adding three hours of wheel running at the start of the dark period (their normal active time) for four days had no additional phase shifting effect on SCN *Per1* expression when exposed to either an eight hour phase advance or delay in light schedule (56). When the exercise is administered at the end of the dark period the results are the same (104). When the light schedule remains constant but exercise is scheduled eight hours before lights off (either voluntary or forced) *Per2* expression in the SCN remains entrained to the light schedule (105).

Human studies looking at central clock timing have shown that depending on the time of day, exercise can have an effect on the following melatonin onset. Phase shifts have been seen in both directions with evening exercise (106-108) but this did not carry through to the following night where the melatonin onset was no longer different to the no exercise group (106). When combined with a change in light schedule, exercise may assist with the re-entrainment of the SCN. When placing subjects onto a 23.67 hour day, twice daily two hour bouts of exercise scheduled three and seven hours after waking were able to significantly advance the melatonin peak when compared to subjects who did not exercise (107). Another set of experiments in which subjects had a nine hours phase delay in their sleep/wake cycle under dim light conditions (< 5 lux), three 45 minute bouts of exercise performed in the evening over seven days produced a significant phase delay of melatonin onset of 3.17 hours when compared to a no exercise group (1.67h phase delay) (109). These findings suggest that while exercise could be used to help the SCN to entrain to a new light schedule, the amount required to make a significant impact is most likely impractical for individuals moving to a different light schedule, such as travellers moving to a different time zone.

When examining the effect of exercise on phase shifting peripheral clocks in animal models a different picture

emerges, with variation in responses between tissues. When the light schedule remains unchanged but exercise is scheduled during the normally inactive period for mice, eight hours before lights off (either voluntary or forced) for four weeks, mouse *Per2* expression in skeletal muscle is phase advanced up to 3 hours but a non-significant phase advance is seen in the lung (105). These results demonstrate that altering the timing of muscle activity has a direct effect on the muscle clocks and the associated increase in oxygen demand may have an influence in lung clocks though the results from this study were not conclusive. As expected, no change in *Per2* expression was seen in the SCN. In humans, changes in gene expression in skeletal muscle after a single bout of resistance exercise showed that at six hours post exercise, there was a modest yet statistically significant upregulation of expression of *Cry1*, *Per2*, and *Bmal1*. As only two time points were examined, it was not possible to determine if gene expression had phase shifted for these clock genes.

When exercise accompanies a change in light schedule, the changes in the rhythms of clock gene expression depend on whether the light schedule is advanced or delayed from baseline. After four days of an eight hours advance in light schedule *Per1* expression in the mouse liver did not entrain to the new light schedule in either the control group or the group that exercised at the start of the dark period (56). However, in the same set of experiments *Per1* expression did entrain to the new light schedule in the lung and skeletal muscle in the exercise group but not in the control group. When light exposure was phase delayed by eight hours both groups showed phase delays in *Per1* expression in all tissues examined but exercise did not significantly affect the rate of phase shift over control. If the exercise is given at the end of the dark period, phase advanced mice no longer show re-entrainment in lung and skeletal muscle after 4 days (104). To date there have been no studies that have studied the effect of activity on peripheral clock timing in humans.

It has been shown that exercise can effect circulating levels of melatonin but results have been mixed with some studies showing an increase (106, 110), a decrease (111), or no change (106, 108, 110) and this appears to be dependent on exercise duration, intensity, and time of day. Therefore, it appears that any possible effects of exercise on peripheral gene expression are unlikely due to melatonin. If exercise can directly affect peripheral clock gene expression a possible

candidate to mediate this effect are glucocorticoids. It has been demonstrated in mice and rats that bouts of increased activity increases corticosterone levels (112).

5.2. Temperature

Mammals display an internally generated circadian temperature cycle controlled by the SCN, both directly by melatonin (50) and indirectly by sleep/wake and activity cycles. The effects of environmental temperature cycles have been examined to see if they also influence circadian rhythmicity. Mice that were exposed to an inverted environmental temperature profile with normal 12L:12D cycle for six days (37°C at night, 24°C during the day) showed no change in SCN rhythmicity, but expression rhythms in the liver were shifted by 9.5 hours. The core body temperature rhythm was also shifted with the normal temperature peak shifted from late afternoon to late evening and activity peak shifted from early evening to early morning. Observations showed that feeding rhythms in these mice also shifted by 6.5 hours as they consumed the majority of their food during the day (51). In addition to the studies that invert the environmental temperature cycle, the effect of a two hour

temperature increase during the light period on peripheral clock timing has been examined in mice (113). *Per2* peak expression immediately after the heat increase was phase advanced in the kidney and submandibular gland but not in the liver. Exposing mice to the two hour temperature increase on two consecutive days saw *Per2* peak expression advance in the liver as well as the kidney and submandibular gland immediately after the exposure to the second temperature increase. When measured 24 hours later, *Per2* peak expression had returned to the same phase as seen before the exposure to the two hour temperature increase. To our knowledge, research on the effects of environmental temperature on central and peripheral clocks has not been conducted in humans.

5.3. Food Timing

It has been shown in mice and rat models that changes in feeding schedule does not have an effect on SCN rhythmicity in light:dark conditions (114-117) or constant darkness (114). There is, however, a suggestion that timed caloric restriction may affect SCN rhythmicity. Mice that had received 66% of average daily caloric intake during their normal sleep period at ZT6 (six hours after lights on) demonstrated a decrease in amplitude of *Per1* expression in the SCN and a phase advance of 1.4 hours when compared to ad libitum fed mice or mice that were given a normocaloric intake at ZT 6 (118). To date there is a lack of human studies looking at the effect of meal timing on SCN rhythmicity.

Animal models examining the effect of food timing on peripheral clocks has been shown to be dependent on the tissue examined. In the rat lung, timed restricted feeding to 4 hours during lights on (when they would normally be asleep) was shown to result in a six hour phase advance in *Per1* expression after seven days with no further shift seen after 19 days (115). When the time food was available was extended to eight hours there was no longer any difference in *Per1* expression when compared to ad libitum fed rats. Restricting feeding in mice to when the lights were on did not alter gene expression in the kidney after four days while in the pancreas the results were not clear (114). In the heart, one study in mice was unable to demonstrate a clear result (114), but others have shown phase advances in a number of clock genes in both mice and rats (117, 119). The most commonly examined tissue in animal studies is the liver. When feeding is restricted to lights on, mouse (114, 120) and

rat (115, 120) models show an almost complete inversion of expression in a number of genes after seven to nine days, while others found this inversion occurs even faster (119). Further restricting feeding to just four hours during lights on gave similar results (115, 116).

When kept under constant light conditions, *Per2* expression in mouse liver, kidney, and submandibular gland showed a decrease in amplitude and a broadening in the distribution in peak phases. While remaining in constant light, timed restricting feeding to what would have been lights off (20:00 – 08:00) was unable to increase the amplitude of expression of *Per2* in these tissues but it did reverse the distribution of peak phases to what is seen in animals kept in light/dark conditions (121).

Whether food timing has an effect on a particular peripheral clock may depend on the types of signals it receives from the SCN. The regular timing of meals in a rhythmic pattern has been demonstrated to maintain clock gene expression rhythmicity and amplitude in the liver of rats when autonomic nervous system and corticosterone inputs from the SCN are abolished (48). Glucose production in the rat liver has been shown to be controlled by sympathetic nerves by the SCN regardless of feeding schedule (33, 34). It has also been shown that when rats are restricted to daytime feeding, *Per1* expression in rat submandibular salivary glands remains in sync with the SCN or becomes arrhythmic (32). The submandibular salivary glands receive direct signalling from sympathetic nerves from the SCN, destruction of this neural pathway in rats causes *Per1* expression shift 180 degrees and entrain to the daytime feeding schedule. In the same rats, liver *Per1* expression was shifted by feeding schedule (32), and this shift has also been shown by others (114, 115, 119, 122-124). Feeding induced increases in temperature could also have an entraining effect on peripheral clocks (46). Further evidence of differential signalling to peripheral clocks has been shown using parabiosis – two mice joined together in order to share their blood supply. Parabiotic pairs of mice consisting of one intact and one with the SCN removed were entrained to a 12L:12D cycle before being released into constant darkness for three days. On examination it was found that the mice with the SCN removed were able to maintain circadian rhythms of clock gene expression in the liver and kidney (suggesting a blood borne signal was responsible) but not in heart, spleen, and skeletal muscle (suggesting possible alternate signalling) (125).

Again, at this point in time there are few data available on the effect of meal timing on peripheral clocks in humans. This, in part, has to do with the ability of researchers to directly access suitable tissues over time to determine if time peripheral clocks are likely to be influenced by the timing of eating. The identification of surrogate markers of peripheral clock activity would assist in observing the possible effects of meal timing in humans.

If feeding patterns are out of sync with central clock timing, these become dominant zeitgeber over SCN in certain peripheral clocks resulting in a slow shift of peripheral clock gene expression to match feeding rhythms, and this has been demonstrated in mouse (114) and rat (115) liver. This slow shift may be SCN-influenced as SCN-lesioned mice have been shown to rapidly invert clock gene expression (one to two days) in response to restricted feeding during the subjective day (120) and may exist in order to prevent a transient shift in feeding from making immediate, lasting changes to the timing of physiological processes (60). In addition, destruction of the SCN or isolating cells from the SCN in mice results in a dampening in amplitude of clock gene expression in the

liver (29, 120, 126). This suggests that even though the timing of peripheral clocks in the liver is determined by the timing of food intake, the SCN still has an effect by influencing the amplitude of gene expression in peripheral tissues.

5.4. Diet Composition

There has also been some interest into the effect of macronutrient composition on central and peripheral clock timing. Mice subjected to a high fat diet showed no change in liver and adipose tissue timing but the amplitude of clock gene expression rhythms was attenuated (15). In rats, parenteral nutrition, specifically glucose, amino acids, and saline administration, has been demonstrated to affect both SCN and liver *Per2* expression (127). Human studies showed that switching from a low fat/high carbohydrate diet to a high fat/low carbohydrate diet had no effect on *Bmal1*, *Nr1d1*, *Per1*, *Per2*, and *Per3* rhythmicity but had a significant effect on amplitude of expression for *Bmal1*, *Per1*, *Per2*, and *Per3* in monocytes (75). This change in expression may be an uncoupling of central and peripheral clock timing that in turn

alters metabolic processes (75).

The effect of caffeine on clock gene expression has been investigated in both animal models and humans. Caffeine is able to elevate cytosolic calcium and therefore likely to influence the timing of clock gene expression through the activation of early transcription factor CREB (Figure 1). In the SCN of mice that have been removed and observed in the lab, short term administration of caffeine given early during the day did not induce phase shifts in *Per2* expression but it did induce phase shifts in *Per2* expression in mouse liver, lung, and kidney. These shifts were dependent on the time of administration, with caffeine given early in the day producing advances and administration late at night producing phase delays (128). In mice, long-term caffeine administration has been shown to cause phase delays in *Per2* expression in livers that have been removed and observed in the lab (128) but phase advances in liver *Per1* and *Per2* and delays in *Bmal1* expression when they remain in the animal (129). Human studies have shown that caffeine can acutely inhibit salivary melatonin levels (130) and when administered three hours prior to habitual bedtime causes a delay in melatonin onset on the following night (131). This shift in SCN timing would have the effect of delaying sleep onset, which in turn could contribute to shortened sleep times. It has yet to be determined what the effect of caffeine administration later into the night might be, whether it might cause a more significant delay or, as is the case with light, a phase advance in SCN timing.

As demonstrated above, there are a number of factors that can alter the timing of central and peripheral clocks, and these factors do not affect timing in all clocks in a uniform manner. As a result, central and peripheral clock timing can become uncoupled and this may lead to undesirable consequences. Observational studies have demonstrated that changes to activity that affect timing such as shiftwork have negative consequences on health such as obesity (132, 133), diabetes (134), metabolic dysfunction (132, 135-137), cardiovascular disease (134), and cancer (134, 138). Metabolic disturbances, such as lowered glucose tolerance, have been observed humans when individuals eat at night (139). This disturbance is presumed to occur because of the misalignment of peripheral clocks as a result of the change in meal timing out of alignment with the timing of the SCN but, as yet, this has not been elucidated in humans. As a result of the change in meal timing, homeostasis is disrupted

and results in changes in leptin release, glucose and energy metabolism, and insulin sensitivity (60). A possible way of offsetting this change in metabolic functioning is by altering meal patterns in shiftworkers so they better fit in with circadian rhythms of nutrient metabolism and glucose tolerance (140). By gaining a better understanding of how these different clocks work, we may be able to develop ways of minimising clock desynchrony and the associated negative outcomes that would otherwise occur.

6. Melatonin – more than just a peripheral clock entrainer

While the SCN controls endogenous levels of melatonin, there is evidence that exogenous melatonin can phase shift the SCN (141), although the mechanism by which melatonin achieves this has not been elucidated. One theory that has been presented is that melatonin does not affect the transcriptional/translational feedback loop directly but instead has an effect on post-translational factors involved with protein breakdown (42). This has been supported by observations in the rat SCN. While melatonin injections did not immediately influence the levels of clock gene expression, significant and differential changes were seen 24 hours later (142). Endogenous melatonin phase-response curves to exogenous melatonin have been established (143) and are 12 hours out of phase with melatonin phase-response curves to light (141, 144) and appear similar to a dark pulse phase-response curve (145).

It is possible that exogenous administration of melatonin could be used to resynchronise central and peripheral clocks when they become out of sync due to factors such as shiftwork and travel, but more research is required.

7. Studies in the blind

While there are suggestions that there may be other non-photic entrainers of the SCN, it is generally not possible to determine whether light exposure is a confounder in these studies (143). An exception to this is with studies in blind human subjects who have lost the ability to perceive light as well as lost their vision. These studies show that even when social activity coincides with the light/dark cycle, the SCN cycles to its own non-light entrained rhythm (free run), ranging from 23.9 – 25.0 hours (146-148) and as a

result these individuals suffer from non-24-hour sleep wake disorder (149). These free running individuals move in and out of sync periodically with environmental light/dark cycle despite scheduling their lives (work, meals, social interactions, sleep) in line with the environment. This demonstrates that the SCN is not entrained by non-photic cues in these individuals (149). In these blind subjects that lack light perception, it has been demonstrated that each individual's free running period is not consistent. In this population the free run period slows and accelerates over time (150, 151). Period shortens as the melatonin onset occurs during the early evening and night while it lengthens as the melatonin onset occurs during the morning and afternoon. This variability in free run period suggests that there are non-photic cues that can influence but not entrain the SCN depending on the time of phase they occur, but current studies have not elucidated what these non-photic cues may be. The long term health implications of non-24-hour sleep wake disorder include increased incidence of severe sleep disturbance, increased fatigue, impaired performance, and decline in mood when SCN timing is not in sync with the environment (148, 149).

In this population, the use of exogenous melatonin has been studied to try and realign the SCN with the environmental light/dark cycle (152-155). As yet, dosage of melatonin, method of delivery, and timing of administration still needs to be refined.

8. Conclusion

There is a growing interest in the different ways our bodies keep time to coordinate processes. Living in a world that is increasingly operating on a 24/7 basis means that individuals are active, eating, and exposed to light at times when our bodies are expecting it to be dark and to be sleeping. Observational studies have highlighted that this change in timing of activities have a number of negative consequences on the health of shiftworkers and strategies are required to lessen these health burdens, both on the individual as well as society. Possible interventions may include controlling the timing of meals of shiftworkers, the use of molecules that can alter circadian timing, such as caffeine or exogenous melatonin, or other behavioural modifications around shift rostering or scheduling exercise. By gaining a clearer understanding of how the central and peripheral clocks are affected by mistimed activity, we may be able to come up with

novel ways to minimise the misalignment and improve the health of those affected.

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10. References

1. Siegel JM. Sleep viewed as a state of adaptive inactivity. *Nat Rev Neurosci.* 2009;10(10):747-753.
2. Ribeiro S. Sleep and plasticity. *Pflugers Archiv Eur J Phy.* 2012;463(1):111-120.
3. Maquet P. The role of sleep in learning and memory. *Science.* 2001;294(5544):1048-1052.
4. McGinty D, Szymusiak R. Keeping cool: a hypothesis about the mechanisms and functions of slow-wave sleep. *Trends Neurosci.* 1990;13(12):480-487.
5. Adam K, Oswald I. Sleep is for tissue restoration. *Clin Med (Lond).* 1977;11(4):376-388.
6. Bryant PA, Trinder J, Curtis N. Sick and tired: Does sleep have a vital role in the immune system? *Nat Rev Immunol.* 2004;4(6):457-467.
7. Berger RJ, Phillips NH. Energy conservation and sleep. *Behav Brain Res.* 1995;69(1-2):65-73.
8. Inoue S, Honda K, Komoda Y. Sleep as neuronal detoxification and restitution. *Behav Brain Res.* 1995;69(1-2):91-96.
9. United States Department of Labor. Americal time use survey 2015. Available from: <http://www.bls.gov/tus/charts/>.
10. Markwald RR, Melanson EL, Smith MR, Higgins J, Perreault L, Eckel RH, et al. Impact of insufficient sleep on total daily energy expenditure, food intake, and weight gain. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2013;110(14):5695-5700.
11. Pilcher JJ, Ginter DR, Sadowsky B. Sleep quality versus sleep quantity: Relationships between sleep and measures of health, well-being and sleepiness in college students. *J Psychosom Res.* 1997;42(6):583-596.

12. Lowrey PL, Takahashi JS. Mammalian circadian biology: elucidating genome-wide levels of temporal organization. *Annu Rev Genom Hum G.* 2004;5:407-441.
13. Yamazaki S, Numano R, Abe M, Hida A, Takahashi RI, Ueda M, et al. Resetting central and peripheral circadian oscillators in transgenic rats. *Science.* 2000;288(5466):682-685.
14. Honma KI, Honma S, Hiroshige T. Response curve, free-running period, and activity time in circadian locomotor rhythm of rats. *Jpn J Physiol.* 1985;35(4):643-658.
15. Kohsaka A, Laposky AD, Ramsey KM, Estrada C, Joshu C, Kobayashi Y, et al. High-fat diet disrupts behavioral and molecular circadian rhythms in mice. *Cell Metab.* 2007;6(5):414-421.
16. Campbell SS, Dawson D, Zulley J. When the human circadian system is caught napping: evidence for endogenous rhythms close to 24 hours. *Sleep.* 1993;16(7):638-640.
17. Czeisler CA, Duffy JF, Shanahan TL, Brown EN, Mitchell JF, Rimmer DW, et al. Stability, precision, and near-24-hour period of the human circadian pacemaker. *Science.* 1999;284(5423):2177-2181.
18. Middleton B, Arendt J, Stone BM. Complex effects of melatonin on human circadian rhythms in constant dim light. *J Biol Rhythms.* 1997;12(5):467-477.
19. Dibner C, Schibler U. Circadian timing of metabolism in animal models and humans. *J Intern Med.* 2015;277(5):513-527.
20. Pittendrigh CS, Daan S. A functional analysis of circadian pacemakers in nocturnal rodents. IV. Entrainment: pacemaker as clock. *J Comp Physiol.* 1976;106(3):291-331.
21. Stepien JM, Kennaway DJ. Phase response relationships between light pulses and the melatonin rhythm in rats. *J Biol Rhythms.* 2001;16(3):234-242.
22. St Hilaire MA, Gooley JJ, Khalsa SBS, Kronauer RE, Czeisler CA, Lockley SW. Human phase response curve to a 1 h pulse of bright white light. *J Physiol.* 2012;590(13):3035-3045.
23. Czeisler CA, Kronauer RE, Allan JS, Duffy JF, Jewett ME, Brown EN, et al. Bright light induction of strong (type 0) resetting of the human circadian pacemaker. *Science.* 1989;244(4910):1328-1333.
24. Chang AM, Santhi N, St Hilaire M, Gronfier C, Bradstreet DS, Duffy JF, et al. Human responses to bright light of different durations. *J Physiol.* 2012;590(13):3103-3112.
25. Zeitzer JM, Dijk DJ, Kronauer RE, Brown EN, Czeisler CA. Sensitivity of the human circadian pacemaker to nocturnal light: melatonin phase resetting and suppression. *J Physiol.* 2000;526(3):695-702.
26. Wright HR, Lack LC, Kennaway DJ. Differential effects of light wavelength in phase advancing the melatonin rhythm. *J Pineal Res.* 2004;36(2):140-144.
27. Guilding C, Hughes AT, Brown TM, Namvar S, Piggins HD. A riot of rhythms: neuronal and glial circadian oscillators in the mediobasal hypothalamus. *Mol Brain.* 2009;2(1):28.
28. Sakamoto K, Nagase T, Fukui H, Horikawa K, Okada T, Tanaka H, et al. Multitissue circadian expression of rat period homolog (*rPer2*) mRNA is governed by the mammalian circadian clock, the suprachiasmatic nucleus in the brain. *J Biol Chem.* 1998;273(42):27039-27042.
29. Akhtar RA, Reddy AB, Maywood ES, Clayton JD, King VM, Smith AG, et al. Circadian cycling of the mouse liver transcriptome, as revealed by cDNA microarray, is driven by the suprachiasmatic nucleus. *Curr Biol.* 2002;12(7):540-550.
30. Terazono H, Mutoh T, Yamaguchi S, Kobayashi M, Akiyama M, Udo R, et al. Adrenergic regulation of clock gene expression in mouse liver. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2003;100(11):6795-6800.
31. Ueyama T, Krout KE, Van Nguyen X, Karpitskiy V, Kollert A, Mettenleiter TC, et al. Suprachiasmatic nucleus: a central autonomic clock. *Nat Neurosci.* 1999;2(12):1051-1053.
32. Vujovic N, Davidson AJ, Menaker M. Sympathetic input modulates, but does not determine, phase of peripheral circadian oscillators. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol.* 2008;295(1):R355-R360.
33. Cailotto C, La Fleur SE, Van Heijningen C, Wortel J, Kalsbeek A, Feenstra M, et al. The suprachiasmatic nucleus controls the daily variation of plasma glucose via the autonomic output to the liver: are the clock genes involved? *European J Neurosci.* 2005;22(10):2531-2540.
34. Kalsbeek A, La Fleur S, Van Heijningen C, Buijs RM.

- Suprachiasmatic GABAergic inputs to the paraventricular nucleus control plasma glucose concentrations in the rat via sympathetic innervation of the liver. *J Neurosci.* 2004;24(35):7604-7613.
35. Cailotto C, Lei J, van der Vliet J, van Heijningen C, van Eden CG, Kalsbeek A, et al. Effects of nocturnal light on (clock) gene expression in peripheral organs: a role for the autonomic innervation of the liver. *PLoS ONE.* 2009;4(5):e5650.
 36. Bando H, Nishio T, Van Der Horst GTJ, Masubuchi S, Hisa Y, Okamura H. Vagal regulation of respiratory clocks in mice. *J Neurosci.* 2007;27(16):4359-4365.
 37. Buijs RM. Anatomical and functional demonstration of a multisynaptic suprachiasmatic nucleus adrenal (cortex) pathway. *Eur J Neurosci.* 1999;11(5):1535-1544.
 38. Ishida A, Mutoh T, Ueyama T, Bando H, Masubuchi S, Nakahara D, et al. Light activates the adrenal gland: Timing of gene expression and glucocorticoid release. *Cell Metabolism.* 2005;2(5):297-307.
 39. Bartness TJ, Song CK, Demas GE. SCN efferents to peripheral tissues: implications for biological rhythms. *J Biol Rhythms.* 2001;16(3):196-204.
 40. Alonso-Vale MIC, Andreotti S, Mukai PY, Borges-Silva CDN, Peres SB, Cipolla-Neto J, et al. Melatonin and the circadian entrainment of metabolic and hormonal activities in primary isolated adipocytes. *J Pineal Res.* 2008;45(4):422-429.
 41. Archer SN, Laing EE, Moller-Levet CS, Van Der Veen DR, Bucca G, Lazar AS, et al. Mistimed sleep disrupts circadian regulation of the human transcriptome. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2014;111(6):E682-E691.
 42. Vriend J, Reiter RJ. Melatonin feedback on clock genes: a theory involving the proteasome. *J Pineal Res.* 2015;58(1):1-11.
 43. Reddy AB, Maywood ES, Karp NA, King VM, Inoue Y, Gonzalez FJ, et al. Glucocorticoid signaling synchronizes the liver circadian transcriptome. *Hepatology.* 2007;45(6):1478-1488.
 44. Yamamoto T, Nakahata Y, Tanaka M, Yoshida M, Soma H, Shinohara K, et al. Acute physical stress elevates mouse Period1 mRNA expression in mouse peripheral tissues via a glucocorticoid-responsive element. *J Biol Chem.* 2005;280(51):42036-42043.
 45. So AYL, Bernal TU, Pillsbury ML, Yamamoto KR, Feldman BJ. Glucocorticoid regulation of the circadian clock modulates glucose homeostasis. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2009;106(41):17582-17587.
 46. Mohawk JA, Green CB, Takahashi JS. Central and peripheral circadian clocks in mammals. *Annu Rev Neurosci.* 2012;35:445-462.
 47. Rosenfeld P, Van Eekelen JAM, Levine S, De Kloet ER. Ontogeny of the Type 2 glucocorticoid receptor in discrete rat brain regions: an immunocytochemical study. *Dev Brain Res.* 1988;42(1):119-127.
 48. Su Y, Cailotto C, Foppen E, Jansen R, Zhang Z, Buijs R, et al. The role of feeding rhythm, adrenal hormones and neuronal inputs in synchronizing daily clock gene rhythms in the liver. *Mol Cell Endocrinol.* 2016;422:125-131.
 49. Balsalobre A, Brown SA, Marcacci L, Tronche F, Kellendonk C, Reichardt HM, et al. Resetting of circadian time in peripheral tissues by glucocorticoid signaling. *Science.* 2000;289(5488):2344-2347.
 50. Cagnacci A, Krauchi K, Wirz-Justice A, Volpe A. Homeostatic versus circadian effects of melatonin on core body temperature in humans. *J Biol Rhythms.* 1997;12(6):509-517.
 51. Brown SA, Zumbrunn G, Fleury-Olela F, Preitner N, Schibler U. Rhythms of mammalian body temperature can sustain peripheral circadian clocks. *Curr Biol.* 2002;12(18):1574-583.
 52. Reinke H, Saini C, Fleury-Olela F, Dibner C, Benjamin IJ, Schibler U. Differential display of DNA-binding proteins reveals heat-shock factor 1 as a circadian transcription factor. *Genes Dev.* 2008;22(3):331-345.
 53. Buhr ED, Yoo SH, Takahashi JS. Temperature as a universal resetting cue for mammalian circadian oscillators. *Science.* 2010;330(6002):379-385.
 54. Aschoff J. Exogenous and endogenous components in circadian rhythms. *Cold Spring Harb Symp Quant Biol.* 1960;25:11-28.
 55. Richter CP. Inborn nature of the rat's 24-hour clock. *J Comp Physiol Psych.* 1971;75(1):1-4.

56. Yamanaka Y, Honma S, Honma K-i. Scheduled exposures to a novel environment with a running-wheel differentially accelerate re-entrainment of mice peripheral clocks to new light-dark cycles. *Genes Cells*. 2008;13(5):497-507.
57. Bjarnason GA, Jordan RCK, Wood PA, Li Q, Lincoln DW, Sothorn RB, et al. Circadian expression of clock genes in human oral mucosa and skin: association with specific cell-cycle phases. *Am J Pathol*. 2001;158(5):1793-1801.
58. Watanabe M, Hida A, Kitamura S, Enomoto M, Ohsawa Y, Katayose Y, et al. Rhythmic expression of circadian clock genes in human leukocytes and beard hair follicle cells. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 2012;425(4):902-907.
59. Janich P, Toufighi K, Solanas G, Luis NM, Minkwitz S, Serrano L, et al. Human epidermal stem cell function is regulated by circadian oscillations. *Cell Stem Cell*. 2013;13(6):745-753.
60. Schibler U, Ripperger J, Brown SA. Peripheral circadian oscillators in mammals: time and food. *J Biol Rhythms*. 2003;18(3):250-260.
61. Akashi M, Soma H, Tsugitomi A, Yamashita S, Yamamoto T, Nishida E, et al. Noninvasive method for assessing the human circadian clock using hair follicle cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2010;107(35):15643-15648.
62. Okamoto A, Yamamoto T, Matsumura R, Node K, Akashi M. An out-of-lab trial: a case example for the effect of intensive exercise on rhythms of human clock gene expression. *J Circadian Rhythms*. 2013;11(1):10.
63. Baird AL, Coogan AN, Siddiqui A, Donev RM, Thome J. Adult attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder is associated with alterations in circadian rhythms at the behavioural, endocrine and molecular levels. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2012;17(10):988-995.
64. Cajochen C, Jud C, Munch M, Kobiacka S, Wirz-Justice A, Albrecht U. Evening exposure to blue light stimulates the expression of the clock gene PER2 in humans. *Eur J Neurosci*. 2006;23(4):1082-1086.
65. Novakova M, Sladek M, Sumova A. Human chronotype is determined in bodily cells under real-life conditions. *Chronobiol Int*. 2013;30(4):607-617.
66. Brown SA, Kunz D, Dumas A, Westermark PO, Vanselow K, Tilmann-Wahnschaffe A, et al. Molecular insights into human daily behavior. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2008;105(5):1602-607.
67. Hasan S, Santhi N, Lazar AS, Slak A, Lo J, Von Schantz M, et al. Assessment of circadian rhythms in humans: Comparison of real-time fibroblast reporter imaging with plasma melatonin. *FASEB J*. 2012;26(6):2414-2423.
68. Lippert J, Halfter H, Heidbreder A, Rohr D, Gess B, Boentert M, et al. Altered dynamics in the circadian oscillation of clock genes in dermal fibroblasts of patients suffering from idiopathic hypersomnia. *PLoS ONE*. 2014;9 (1):e85255.
69. Sandu C, Dumas M, Malan A, Sambakhe D, Marteau C, Nizard C, et al. Human skin keratinocytes, melanocytes, and fibroblasts contain distinct circadian clock machineries. *Cell Mol Life Sci*. 2012;69(19):3329-3339.
70. Burioka N, Koyanagi S, Endo M, Takata M, Fukuoka Y, Miyata M, et al. Clock gene dysfunction in patients with obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome. *Eur Respir J*. 2008;32(1):105-112.
71. Lech K, Ackermann K, Revell VL, Lao O, Skene DJ, Kayser M. Dissecting daily and circadian expression rhythms of clock-controlled genes in human blood. *J Biol Rhythms*. 2016;31(1):68-81.
72. Moller-Levet CS, Archer SN, Bucca G, Laing EE, Slak A, Kabiljo R, et al. Effects of insufficient sleep on circadian rhythmicity and expression amplitude of the human blood transcriptome. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2013;110(12):E1132-E1141.
73. Takimoto M, Hamada A, Tomoda A, Ohdo S, Ohmura T, Sakato H, et al. Daily expression of clock genes in whole blood cells in healthy subjects and a patient with circadian rhythm sleep disorder. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol*. 2005;289(5 58-5):R1273-R1279.
74. Zhu Y, Fu A, Hoffman AE, Figueiro MG, Carskadon MA, Sharkey KM, et al. Advanced sleep schedules affect circadian gene expression in young adults with delayed sleep schedules. *Sleep Med*. 2013;14(5):449-455.
75. Pivovarovova O, Jurchott K, Rudovich N, Hornemann S, Ye L, Mockel S, et al. Changes of dietary fat and carbohydrate content alter central and peripheral clock in humans. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2015;100(6):2291-2302.

76. Boivin DB, James FO, Wu A, Cho-Park PF, Xiong H, Sun ZS. Circadian clock genes oscillate in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *Blood*. 2003;102(12):4143-4145.
77. Cuesta M, Cermakian N, Boivin DB. Glucocorticoids entrain molecular clock components in human peripheral cells. *FASEB J*. 2015;29(4):1360-1370.
78. Ebisawa T, Numazawa K, Shimada H, Izutsu H, Sasaki T, Kato N, et al. Self-sustained circadian rhythm in cultured human mononuclear cells isolated from peripheral blood. *Neurosci Res*. 2010;66(2):223-227.
79. Huang MC, Ho CW, Chen CH, Liu SC, Chen CC, Leu SJ. Reduced expression of circadian clock genes in male alcoholic patients. *Alcohol Clin Exp Res*. 2010;34(11):1899-1904.
80. James FO, Boivin DB, Charbonneau S, Belanger V, Cermakian N. Expression of clock genes in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells throughout the sleep/wake and circadian cycles. *Chronobiol Int*. 2007;24(6):1009-1034.
81. Kavcic P, Rojc B, Dolenc-Groselj L, Claustrat B, Fujs K, Poljak M. The impact of sleep deprivation and nighttime light exposure on clock gene expression in humans. *Croat Med J*. 2011;52(5):594-603.
82. Kusanagi H, Hida A, Satoh K, Echizenya M, Shimizu T, Pendergast JS, et al. Expression profiles of 10 circadian clock genes in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *Neurosci Res*. 2008;61(2):136-142.
83. Kusanagi H, Mishima K, Satoh K, Echizenya M, Katoh T, Shimizu T. Similar profiles in human period1 gene expression in peripheral mononuclear and polymorphonuclear cells. *Neurosci Lett*. 2004;365(2):124-127.
84. Teboul M, Barrat-Petit MA, Li XM, Claustrat B, Formento JL, Delaunay F, et al. Atypical patterns of circadian clock gene expression in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *J Mol Med*. 2005;83(9):693-699.
85. Yang MY, Yang WC, Lin PM, Hsu JF, Hsiao HH, Liu YC, et al. Altered expression of circadian clock genes in human chronic myeloid leukemia. *J Biol Rhythms*. 2011;26(2):136-148.
86. Ackermann K, Plomp R, Lao O, Middleton B, Revell VL, Skene DJ, et al. Effect of sleep deprivation on rhythms of clock gene expression and melatonin in humans. *Chronobiol Int*. 2013;30(7):901-909.
87. Ackermann K, Sletten TL, Revell VL, Archer SN, Skene DJ. Blue-Light phase shifts PER3 gene expression in human leukocytes. *Chronobiol Int*. 2009;26(4):769-779.
88. Archer SN, Viola AU, Kyriakopoulou V, Von Schantz M, Dijk DJ. Inter-individual differences in habitual sleep timing and entrained phase of endogenous circadian rhythms of BMAL1, PER2 and PER3 mRNA in human leukocytes. *Sleep*. 2008;31(5):608-617.
89. Cai Y, Liu S, Sothorn RB, Xu S, Chan P. Expression of clock genes Per1 and Bmal1 in total leukocytes in health and Parkinson's disease. *Eur J Neurol*. 2010;17(4):550-554.
90. Haimovich B, Calvano J, Haimovich AD, Calvano SE, Coyle SM, Lowry SF. In vivo endotoxin synchronizes and suppresses clock gene expression in human peripheral blood leukocytes. *Crit Care Med*. 2010;38(3):751-758.
91. Reszka E, Peplonska B, Wiecek E, Sobala W, Bukowska A, Gromadzinska J, et al. Circadian gene expression in peripheral blood leukocytes of rotating night shift nurses. *Scand J Work, Environ Health*. 2013;39(2):187-194.
92. Bracci M, Manzella N, Copertaro A, Staffolani S, Barbaresi IM, Strafella E, et al. Rotating-shift nurses after a day off: peripheral clock gene expression, urinary melatonin, and serum 17-beta-estradiol levels. *Scand J Work Environ Health*. 2014;40(3):295-304.
93. Baumann A, Gonnenwein S, Bischoff SC, Sherman H, Chapnik N, Froy O, et al. The circadian clock is functional in eosinophils and mast cells. *Immunology*. 2013;140(4):465-474.
94. Bollinger T, Leutz A, Leliavski A, Skrum L, Kovac J, Bonacina L, et al. Circadian clocks in mouse and human CD4+ T cells. *PLoS ONE*. 2011;6(12):e29801.
95. Leibetseder V, Humpeler S, Svoboda M, Schmid D, Thalhammer T, Zuckermann A, et al. Clock genes display rhythmic expression in human hearts. *Chronobiol Int*. 2009;26(4):621-636.
96. Saini C, Petrenko V, Pulimeno P, Giovannoni L, Berney T, Hebrok M, et al. A functional circadian clock is required for proper insulin secretion by human pancreatic islet

- cells. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2016;18(4):355-365.
97. Gomez-Abellan P, Diez-Noguera A, Madrid JA, Lujan JA, Ordovas JM, Garaulet M. Glucocorticoids affect 24 h clock genes expression in human adipose tissue explant cultures. *PLoS ONE*. 2012;7(12):e50435.
98. Gomez-Abellan P, Hernandez-Morante JJ, Lujan JA, Madrid JA, Garaulet M. Clock genes are implicated in the human metabolic syndrome. *Int J Obes*. 2008;32(1):121-128.
99. Tsinkalovsky O, Smaaland R, Rosenlund B, Sothorn RB, Hirt A, Steine S, et al. Circadian variations in clock gene expression of human bone marrow CD34+ cells. *J Biol Rhythms*. 2007;22(2):140-150.
100. Scheer FAJL, Buijs RM. Light affects morning salivary cortisol in humans. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 1999;84(9):3395-3398.
101. Leproult R, Colecchia EF, L'Hermite-Baleriaux M, Van Cauter E. Transition from dim to bright light in the morning induces an immediate elevation of cortisol levels. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2001;86(1):151-157.
102. Qian J, Block GD, Colwell CS, Matveyenko AV. Consequences of exposure to light at night on the pancreatic islet circadian clock and function in rats. *Diabetes*. 2013;62(10):3469-3478.
103. Kiessling S, Eichele G, Oster H. Adrenal glucocorticoids have a key role in circadian resynchronization in a mouse model of jet lag. *J Clin Invest*. 2010;120(7):2600-2609.
104. Yamanaka Y, Honma S, Honma K-i. Mistimed wheel running interferes with re-entrainment of circadian Per1 rhythms in the mouse skeletal muscle and lung. *Genes Cells*. 2016;21(3):264-274.
105. Wolff G, Esser KA. Scheduled exercise phase shifts the circadian clock in skeletal muscle. *Med Sci Sports Exerc*. 2012;44(9):1663-1670.
106. Buxton OM, Lee CW, L'Hermite-Baleriaux M, Turek FW, Van Cauter E. Exercise elicits phase shifts and acute alterations of melatonin that vary with circadian phase. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol*. 2003;284(3):R714-R724.
107. Miyazaki T, Hashimoto S, Masubuchi S, Honma S, Honma KI. Phase-advance shifts of human circadian pacemaker are accelerated by daytime physical exercise. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol*. 2001;281(1):R197-R205.
108. Van Reeth O, Sturis J, Byrne MM, Blackman JD, L'Hermite-Baleriaux M, Leproult R, et al. Nocturnal exercise phase delays circadian rhythms of melatonin and thyrotropin secretion in normal men. *Am J Physiol Endocrin Metab*. 1994;266(6):E964-E974.
109. Barger LK, Wright Jr KP, Hughes RJ, Czeisler CA. Daily exercise facilitates phase delays of circadian melatonin rhythm in very dim light. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol*. 2004;286(6):R1077-R1084.
110. Buxton OM, Frank SA, L'Hermite-Baleriaux M, Leproult R, Turek FW, Van Cauter E. Roles of intensity and duration of nocturnal exercise in causing phase delays of human circadian rhythms. *Am J Physiol Endocrin Metab*. 1997;273(3):E536-E542.
111. Monteleone P, Maj M, Fusco M, Orazzo C, Kemali D. Physical exercise at night blunts the nocturnal increase of plasma melatonin levels in healthy humans. *Life Sci*. 1990;47(22):1989-1995.
112. Hennessy MB. Sensitization of the plasma corticosterone response to novel environments. *Physiol Behav*. 1991;50(6):1175-1179.
113. Ohnishi N, Tahara Y, Kuriki D, Haraguchi A, Shibata S. Warm water bath stimulates phase-shifts of the peripheral circadian clocks in PER2::LUCIFERASE mouse. *PLoS ONE*. 2014;9(6):e100272.
114. Damiola F, Le Minli N, Preitner N, Kornmann B, Fleury-Olela F, Schibler U. Restricted feeding uncouples circadian oscillators in peripheral tissues from the central pacemaker in the suprachiasmatic nucleus. *Genes Dev*. 2000;14(23):2950-2961.
115. Stokkan KA, Yamazaki S, Tei H, Sakaki Y, Menaker M. Entrainment of the circadian clock in the liver by feeding. *Science*. 2001;291(5503):490-493.
116. Hara R, Wan K, Wakamatsu H, Aida R, Moriya T, Akiyama M, et al. Restricted feeding entrains liver clock without participation of the suprachiasmatic nucleus. *Genes Cells*. 2001;6(3):269-278.
117. Oishi K, Miyazaki K, Ishida N. Functional CLOCK is not involved in the entrainment of peripheral clocks to the

- restricted feeding: entrainable expression of mPer2 and BMAL1 mRNAs in the heart of Clock mutant mice on jcl:ICR background. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2002;298(2):198-202.
118. Mendoza J, Graff C, Dardente H, Pevet P, Challet E. Feeding cues alter clock gene oscillations and photic responses in the suprachiasmatic nuclei of mice exposed to a light/dark cycle. *J Neurosci.* 2005;25(6):1514-1522.
119. Wu T, Jin Y, Ni Y, Zhang D, Kato H, Fu Z. Effects of light cues on re-entrainment of the food-dominated peripheral clocks in mammals. *Gene.* 2008;419(1-2):27-34.
120. Saini C, Liani A, Curie T, Gos P, Kreppel F, Emmenegger Y, et al. Real-time recording of circadian liver gene expression in freely moving mice reveals the phase-setting behavior of hepatocyte clocks. *Genes Dev.* 2013;27(13):1526-1536.
121. Hamaguchi Y, Tahara Y, Hitosugi M, Shibata S. Impairment of circadian rhythms in peripheral clocks by constant light is partially reversed by scheduled feeding or exercise. *J Biol Rhythms.* 2015;30(6):533-542.
122. Oishi K, Kasamatsu M, Ishida N. Gene- and tissue-specific alterations of circadian clock gene expression in streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice under restricted feeding. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2004;317(2):330-334.
123. Sujino M, Furukawa K, Koinuma S, Fujioka A, Nagano M, Iigo M, et al. Differential entrainment of peripheral clocks in the rat by glucocorticoid and feeding. *Endocrinology.* 2012;153(5):2277-2286.
124. Yoshida C, Shikata N, Seki S, Koyama N, Noguchi Y. Early nocturnal meal skipping alters the peripheral clock and increases lipogenesis in mice. *Nutr Metab.* 2012;9:78.
125. Guo H, Brewer JM, Champhekar A, Harris RBS, Bittman EL. Differential control of peripheral circadian rhythms by suprachiasmatic-dependent neural signals. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2005;102(8):3111-3116.
126. Hughes ME, DiTacchio L, Hayes KR, Vollmers C, Pulivarthy S, Baggs JE, et al. Harmonics of circadian gene transcription in mammals. *PLoS Genetics.* 2009;5(4):e1000442.
127. Iwanaga H, Yano M, Miki H, Okada K, Azama T, Takiguchi S, et al. Per2 gene expressions in the suprachiasmatic nucleus and liver differentially respond to nutrition factors in rats. *J Parenter Enteral Nutr.* 2005;29(3):157-161.
128. Narishige S, Kuwahara M, Shinozaki A, Okada S, Ikeda Y, Kamagata M, et al. Effects of caffeine on circadian phase, amplitude and period evaluated in cells in vitro and peripheral organs in vivo in PER2::LUCIFERASE mice. *Br J Pharmacol.* 2014;171(24):5858-5869.
129. Sherman H, Gutman R, Chapnik N, Meylan J, Le Coutre J, Froy O. Caffeine alters circadian rhythms and expression of disease and metabolic markers. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol.* 2011;43(5):829-838.
130. Wright KP, Jr., Badia P, Myers BL, Plenzler SC, Hakel M. Caffeine and light effects on nighttime melatonin and temperature levels in sleep-deprived humans. *Brain Res.* 1997;747(1):78-84.
131. Burke TM, Markwald RR, McHill AW, Chinoy ED, Snider JA, Bessman SC, et al. Effects of caffeine on the human circadian clock in vivo and in vitro. *Sci Transl Med.* 2015;7(305):5125.
132. Karlsson B, Knutsson A, Lindahl B. Is there an association between shift work and having a metabolic syndrome? Results from a population based study of 27 485 people. *Occup Environ Med.* 2001;58(11):747-752.
133. Di Lorenzo L, De Pergola G, Zocchetti C, L'Abbate N, Basso A, Pannacciulli N, et al. Effect of shift work on body mass index: results of a study performed in 319 glucose-tolerant men working in a Southern Italian industry. *Int J Obes.* 2003;27(11):1353-1358.
134. Wang XS, Armstrong MEG, Cairns BJ, Key TJ, Travis RC. Shift work and chronic disease: the epidemiological evidence. *Occup Med.* 2011;61(2):78-89.
135. Karlsson BH, Knutsson AK, Lindahl BO, Alfredsson LS. Metabolic disturbances in male workers with rotating three-shift work. Result of the WOLF study. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health.* 2003;76(6):424-430.
136. Al-Naimi S, Hampton SM, Richard P, Tzung C, Morgan LM. Postprandial metabolic profiles following meals and snacks eaten during simulated night and day shift work. *Chronobiol Int.* 2004;21(6):937-947.
137. Lund J, Arendt J, Hampton SM, English J, Morgan LM. Postprandial hormone and metabolic responses

- amongst shift workers in Antarctica. *J Endocrinol.* 2001;171(3):557-564.
138. Erren TC, Pape HG, Reiter RJ, Piekarski C. Chronodisruption and cancer. *Naturwissenschaften.* 2008;95(5):367-382.
139. Morris CJ, Yang JN, Garcia JI, Myers S, Bozzi I, Wang W, et al. Endogenous circadian system and circadian misalignment impact glucose tolerance via separate mechanisms in humans. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2015;112(17):E2225-E2234.
140. Grant C, Coates A, Dorrian J, Kennaway D, Wittert G, Heilbronn L, et al. Eating on simulated night shift effects glucose response to breakfast: pilot study. *FASEB J.* 2016;30(1(suppl)):1160.2.
141. Lewy AJ, Bauer VK, Ahmed S, Thomas KH, Cutler NL, Singer CM, et al. The human phase response curve (PRC) to melatonin is about 12 hours out of phase with the PRC to light. *Chronobiol Int.* 1998;15(1):71-83.
142. Poirel VJ, Boggio V, Dardente H, Pevet P, Masson-Pevet M, Gauer F. Contrary to other non-photoc cues, acute melatonin injection does not induce immediate changes of clock gene mRNA expression in the rat suprachiasmatic nuclei. *Neurosci.* 2003;120(3):745-755.
143. Mistlberger RE, Skene DJ. Nonphotic entrainment in humans? *J Biol Rhythms.* 2005;20(4):339-352.
144. Skene DJ. Optimization of light and melatonin to phase-shift human circadian rhythms. *J Neuroendocrinol.* 2003;15(4):438-441.
145. Boulos Z, Rusak B. Circadian phase response curves for dark pulses in the hamster. *J Comp Physiol.* 1982;146(4):411-417.
146. Lockley SW, Skene DJ, Arendt J, Tabandeh H, Bird AC, DeFrance R. Relationship between melatonin rhythms and visual loss in the blind. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 1997;82(11):3763-3770.
147. Sack RL, Lewy AJ, Blood ML, Keith LD, Nakagawa H. Circadian rhythm abnormalities in totally blind people: Incidence and clinical significance. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 1992;75(1):127-134.
148. Skene DJ, Lockley SW, Thapan K, Arendt J. Effects of light on human circadian rhythms. *Reprod Nutr Dev.* 1999;39(3):295-304.
149. Lockley SW, Dijk DJ, Kosti O, Skene DJ, Arendt J. Alertness, mood and performance rhythm disturbances associated with circadian sleep disorders in the blind. *J Sleep Res.* 2008;17(2):207-216.
150. Emens JS, Lewy AJ, Lefler BJ, Sack RL. Relative coordination to unknown "weak zeitgebers" in free-running blind individuals. *J Biol Rhythms.* 2005;20(2):159-167.
151. Emens JS, Laurie AL, Songer JB, Lewy AJ. Non-24-hour disorder in blind individuals revisited: variability and the influence of environmental time cues. *Sleep.* 2013;36(7):1091-1100.
152. Lockley SW, Skene DJ, James K, Thapan K, Wright J, Arendt J. Melatonin administration can entrain the free-running circadian system of blind subjects. *J Endocrinol.* 2000;164(1):R1-R6.
153. Sack RL, Brandes RW, Kendall AR, Lewy AJ. Entrainment of free-running circadian rhythms by melatonin in blind people. *N Engl J Med.* 2000;343(15):1070-1077.
154. Hack LM, Lockley SW, Arendt J, Skene DJ. The effects of low-dose 0.5-mg melatonin on the free-running circadian rhythms of blind subjects. *J Biol Rhythms.* 2003;18(5):420-429.
155. Roth T, Nir T, Zisapel N. Prolonged release melatonin for improving sleep in totally blind subjects: a pilot placebo-controlled multicenter trial. *Nat Sci Sleep.* 2015;7:13-23.